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It does not include any clear assertion.

I have no intention of proving any clear assertion in the future.

Diestel, J. and Uhl, J. J., Jr., *Vector measures*.

Yagisita, Hiroki, *Heat equation and Schrödinger equation with translation invariance on the infinite-dimensional vector space \mathbb{R}^∞* .

Let H be a complex Hilbert space. So, it seems best to think of integral of H -valued function as Pettis integral. Let Ω be a measurable space. Then, let $S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; H)$ denote the set (possibly, the complex Hilbert space) of all maps Φ such that there exist a finite measure μ and an H -valued function f such that for any measurable set Λ , $\Phi(\Lambda) = \int_{\Lambda} \|f\|_H f d\mu$ holds.

(1) $S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; \mathbb{C}) = CM(\Omega)$ holds. However, it seems that it can be further considered as $CM(\Omega) \subset S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; CM(\Omega))$. In other words, for $|f|f d\mu \in CM(\Omega)$, we make $[\Lambda \mapsto |f|f 1_{\Lambda} d\mu] \in S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; CM(\Omega))$ correspond. It is the intention to make the quantum state when information that it is in Λ is obtained correspond.

(2) Let E be a spectral measure on Ω of H . Then, it seems that it can be considered as $H \subset S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; H)$. In other words, for $u \in H$, we make $[\Lambda \mapsto E(\Lambda)u] \in S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; H)$ correspond. It is also the intention to make the quantum state when information that it is in Λ is obtained correspond.

In other words, (1) can be considered an important special case of (2). After all, one might say that a quantum ideal measurement is a spectral measure on a measurable space. Self-adjoint operator is important as Hamiltonian. On the other hand, in quantum measurement, it seems that there are many cases where a real number has no meaning beyond labeling. Let G be a complex Hilbert space. As a not necessarily ideal quantum measurement, one might consider a map from H to $S^{\frac{1}{2}}(\Omega; G)$.